

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD FOR CONSTRUCTING A MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF A HYDROGENATION OIL CLEANING INSTALLATION

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Abstract

At present, the complexity and difficult formalization of the objects under study leads to the need to build their mathematical models designed to predict the behavior of a real object. If the decision to create a model is made, then proceed to the stage of examining the modeling object. The main purpose of this stage is to prepare a meaningful statement of the modeling problem. The list of basic questions about the modeling object formulated in a meaningful (verbal) form constitutes a meaningful statement of the modeling problem, including a various mathematical relationships set that describe the behavior and properties of the modeling object. Mathematical models in a quantitative form, with the help of logical and mathematical constructions, describe the main properties of an object, process or system, its parameters, internal and external connections.

Keywords: mathematical model, technological process, process control, regression model, hydrotreating process.

One of the important problems in the study and optimization of any technological object functioning is the construction of its mathematical model [1÷5]. Let us construct a mathematical model for the functioning of a hydrogenation oil refining installation, which takes into account the hydrogen concentration parameter in a hydrogen-containing gas (HCG) [6]. To build a mathematical model, the necessary steps are to study the processes occurring at the installation, determine the factors (parameters) that have the greatest influence on the course of the technological process, select the mathematical model type, and collect statistical data that determine the current state of the object under study in time [7, 8].

The technological process of contaminated oils purification occurs in the HCG presence, and the pollutants are sulfur, nitrogen and oxygen-containing compounds. The hydrotreating process purpose is to reduce the amount of components that pollute the oil, improve its quality characteristics (density, viscosity, viscosity index, etc.), as well as increase its chemical resistance.

In the process under consideration, contaminated oil is supplied for mixing with HCG and then enters the heating elements, where it is heated to a temperature of 260÷350 °C. Next, the heated feed gas mixture enters the reactor, where the main reactions associated with purification take place. After purification, the mixture enters the separator and the stripping column, where the purified oil is sequentially separated from the by-products of the mixture and further transported to the finished product park. The amount of HCG supplied for mixing and the hydrogen concentration in it, as well as the other technological parameters values, are strictly regulated.

On Fig. 1 shows a hydrotreating process automation functional diagram. As can be seen from Fig. 1, the

process control is carried out according to six parameters: x_1 - the flow rate of raw materials at the inlet to the installation (m^3/h), x_2 - the flow rate of HCG supplied to the mixing (m^3/h), x_3 - the pressure at the inlet to the stripping column K-1/1 (kgf/sm^2 , for the 2nd mathematical model - kPa), x_4 - steam consumption in the K-1/1 stripping column (kg/h), x_5 - bottom temperature of the K-1/1 stripping column ($^{\circ}C$), x_6 is the hydrogen amount in the HCG mixed with the feed (m^3/h). It also measures the viscosity at 50 °C of the purified oil to determine its quality.

The catalyst used in the process under study is made of cobalt-molybdenum-aluminum. Despite the fact that one of the main devices in the technological complex under consideration is the reactor, its parameters are not controlled due to the processes complexity occurring in it and a fairly large factors number affecting the reactions course, including: catalysts activity, reaction time, as well as other indicators that can take on different values depending on the position in time and space.

Due to the above, it is impossible to directly influence the processes occurring inside the reactor and, therefore, the parameters that are measured in it will not be included in the mathematical model.

To construct a mathematical model, a regression model was chosen as the basis. The regression model development requires regression analysis, which is a statistical research method that consists in determining the dependence of the dependent variable Y on the independent variable X or the independent variables set of $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\}$.

In general, these equations have the form:

$$Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) \quad (1)$$

There are linear and non-linear regression models. Linear equations include equations of the form:

$$Y = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Automation functional diagram

Non-linear models, in turn, are divided into: nonlinear with respect to independent variables, but linear with respect to the equation coefficients (polynomials of the 2nd and 3rd degree, hyperbola, etc.) and models that are non-linear with respect to the equation coefficients (power, exponential, exponential, etc.). In our case, a mathematical model was chosen in the form of a 2nd degree polynomial, which in the general case has the form:

$$Y = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2^2 \quad (3)$$

Taking into account the fact that six parameters are chosen, we have:

$$a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_{11}x_1^2 + a_2x_2 + a_{22}x_2^2 + a_3x_3 + a_{33}x_3^2 + a_4x_4 + a_{44}x_4^2 + a_5x_5 + a_{55}x_5^2 + a_6x_6 + a_{66}x_6^2 = y \quad (4)$$

To find the regression equation coefficients, we use the least squares method, which is based on the function of minimizing the square of the difference between the current and calculated values for the mathematical equation parameters. It is one of the main ones in regression analysis and its essence is reflected by an expression of the form:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_{it} - x_{ip})^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (5)$$

where x_{it} it is the current (real) parameter value, x_{ip} is the calculated (model) parameter value.

The next step is to find the partial derivatives of the function (5) with respect to each of the independent

input variables and equate them to 0, which is represented by the expression:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial x_i} = 0, \text{ где } i = (1, n) \quad (6)$$

Thus, a equations system is obtained, the solution of which leads to finding the coefficients of this regression equation.

The mathematical model is constructed on the basis of statistical data collected at a functioning enterprise (Table 1). The system was solved by the Cramer method, which is used when the equations number in the system coincides with the unknowns number and the main determinant of the coefficient matrix is different from 0. When the above conditions are met, the system has the only existing solution.

Consider the application of this method for the case when the model is a polynomial of the 2nd degree. In this case, the system can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} n & x & x^2 \\ x & x^2 & x^3 \\ x^2 & x^3 & x^4 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y \\ yx \\ yx^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $\begin{bmatrix} n & x & x^2 \\ x & x^2 & x^3 \\ x^2 & x^3 & x^4 \end{bmatrix}$ - the main determinant of the matrix and is denoted by Δ .

By replacing the corresponding columns of the matrix with $\begin{bmatrix} y \\ yx \\ yx^2 \end{bmatrix}$ find the determinants, denoted respectively $\Delta_0, \Delta_1, \Delta_2$, in which the replacement of the

column corresponding to the index by the right side of the equality is carried out. The equation coefficients are found by dividing these determinants by the main determinant:

$$a_0 = \frac{\Delta_0}{\Delta}, a_1 = \frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta}, a_2 = \frac{\Delta_2}{\Delta} \quad (8)$$

We will do the same with the resulting system consisting of 13 equations and having 13 unknowns. Let's imagine the system in the matrix form, the calculation of the elements numerical values of which will be performed in the Microsoft Office Excel program.

As shown in the example with a polynomial of the 2nd degree, we will carry out similar calculations of the

main determinant and the matrices determinants of with columns successively replaced by the equation right side, respectively, according to the index.

There are different methods for finding the matrices determinants: expanding the determinant by the row or column elements, bringing the determinant to a triangular form, etc.

When using the expanding a matrix by row or column method to determine its determinant, if the matrix has a dimension of n*n, you will have to calculate the sum of n! terms.

Table 1

Statistical data

X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	Y
20,4	8103	95	134	160	6629	35
18,5	7789	95,5	121	161	6818	32,4
18,5	8045	96	130	162	6519	32,2
18,6	8271	96,5	133	163	7028	34,4
18,8	8330	97	134	164	6629	34,2
19,9	5107	97,5	140	165	4357	34
19,2	8184	98	128	166	6673	34,6
19,2	7855	98,5	128	167	6827	34,4
19,6	8547	99	133	168	6619	34,2
19,8	8103	99,5	129	169	7254	33,2
19,9	8271	100	130	170	6492	33
20,2	8330	100,5	131	171	7169	32,8
20,4	5107	101	132	161	4592	32,7
18,5	7797	101,5	133	162	6791	32,4
19,9	7789	102	134	174	6629	32,2
18,2	8547	102,5	135	175	7351	34,2
18,5	7855	103	128	167	6827	33,2
19,6	8045	103,5	137	168	6834	31,6
19,8	7797	104	129	169	6619	31,3
19,9	8184	105	140	180	7254	31

$$\begin{vmatrix}
 n & x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4 & x_5 & x_6 & x_1^2 & x_2^2 & x_3^2 & x_4^2 & x_5^2 & x_6^2 \\
 x_1 & x_1^2 & x_1x_2 & x_1x_3 & x_1x_4 & x_1x_5 & x_1x_6 & x_1^3 & x_1x_2^2 & x_1x_3^2 & x_1x_4^2 & x_1x_5^2 & x_1x_6^2 \\
 x_2 & x_1x_2 & x_2^2 & x_2x_3 & x_2x_4 & x_2x_5 & x_2x_6 & x_1^2x_2 & x_2^3 & x_2x_3^2 & x_2x_4^2 & x_2x_5^2 & x_2x_6^2 \\
 x_3 & x_1x_3 & x_2x_3 & x_3^2 & x_3x_4 & x_3x_5 & x_3x_6 & x_1^2x_3 & x_2^2x_3 & x_3^3 & x_3x_4^2 & x_3x_5^2 & x_3x_6^2 \\
 x_4 & x_1x_4 & x_2x_4 & x_3x_4 & x_4^2 & x_4x_5 & x_4x_6 & x_1^2x_4 & x_2^2x_4 & x_3^2x_4 & x_4^3 & x_4x_5^2 & x_4x_6^2 \\
 x_5 & x_1x_5 & x_2x_5 & x_3x_5 & x_4x_5 & x_5^2 & x_5x_6 & x_1^2x_5 & x_2^2x_5 & x_3^2x_5 & x_4^2x_5 & x_5^3 & x_5x_6^2 \\
 x_6 & x_1x_6 & x_2x_6 & x_3x_6 & x_4x_6 & x_5x_6 & x_6^2 & x_1^2x_6 & x_2^2x_6 & x_3^2x_6 & x_4^2x_6 & x_5^2x_6 & x_6^3 \\
 x_1^2 & x_1^3 & x_1^2x_2 & x_1^2x_3 & x_1^2x_4 & x_1^2x_5 & x_1^2x_6 & x_1^4 & x_1^2x_2^2 & x_1^2x_3^2 & x_1^2x_4^2 & x_1^2x_5^2 & x_1^2x_6^2 \\
 x_2^2 & x_1x_2^2 & x_2^3 & x_2^2x_3 & x_2^2x_4 & x_2^2x_5 & x_2^2x_6 & x_1^2x_2^2 & x_2^4 & x_2^2x_3^2 & x_2^2x_4^2 & x_2^2x_5^2 & x_2^2x_6^2 \\
 x_3^2 & x_1x_3^2 & x_2x_3^2 & x_3^3 & x_3^2x_4 & x_3^2x_5 & x_3^2x_6 & x_1^2x_3^2 & x_2^2x_3^2 & x_3^4 & x_3^2x_4^2 & x_3^2x_5^2 & x_3^2x_6^2 \\
 x_4^2 & x_1x_4^2 & x_2x_4^2 & x_3x_4^2 & x_4^3 & x_4^2x_5 & x_4^2x_6 & x_1^2x_4^2 & x_2^2x_4^2 & x_3^2x_4^2 & x_4^4 & x_4^2x_5^2 & x_4^2x_6^2 \\
 x_5^2 & x_1x_5^2 & x_2x_5^2 & x_3x_5^2 & x_4x_5^2 & x_5^3 & x_5^2x_6 & x_1^2x_5^2 & x_2^2x_5^2 & x_3^2x_5^2 & x_4^2x_5^2 & x_5^4 & x_5^2x_6^2 \\
 x_6^2 & x_1x_6^2 & x_2x_6^2 & x_3x_6^2 & x_4x_6^2 & x_5x_6^2 & x_6^3 & x_1^2x_6^2 & x_2^2x_6^2 & x_3^2x_6^2 & x_4^2x_6^2 & x_5^2x_6^2 & x_6^4
 \end{vmatrix}^*$$

$$\begin{matrix}
 a_0 \\
 a_1 \\
 a_{11} \\
 a_2 \\
 a_{22} \\
 a_3 \\
 a_{33} \\
 a_4 \\
 a_{44} \\
 a_5 \\
 a_{55} \\
 a_6 \\
 a_{66}
 \end{matrix}
 *
 \begin{matrix}
 y \\
 x_1 y \\
 x_1^2 y \\
 x_2 y \\
 x_2^2 y \\
 x_3 y \\
 x_3^2 y \\
 x_4 y \\
 x_4^2 y \\
 x_5 y \\
 x_5^2 y \\
 x_6 y \\
 x_6^2 y
 \end{matrix}
 =
 \begin{matrix}
 y \\
 x_1 y \\
 x_1^2 y \\
 x_2 y \\
 x_2^2 y \\
 x_3 y \\
 x_3^2 y \\
 x_4 y \\
 x_4^2 y \\
 x_5 y \\
 x_5^2 y \\
 x_6 y \\
 x_6^2 y
 \end{matrix}
 \quad (9)$$

Since our matrix has a 11*11 dimension, we use the reduction to a triangular form method. By dividing the determinants of matrices with replaced columns by the matrix main determinant, we obtain the coefficients values of the mathematical model described by the regression equation. The numerical values of the coefficients are presented in the system below:

$$\begin{cases}
 a_0 = 35.150453840961281381 \\
 a_1 = -0.01947314147950391 \\
 a_2 = 0.0015485321281696507 \\
 a_3 = -0.00015111547700513 \\
 a_4 = 0.005633629965215796 \\
 a_5 = -0.001210291478275149 \\
 a_6 = -0.0000275368935526 \\
 a_{11} = -0.00292586360758979 \\
 a_{22} = -0.000000760152978526 \\
 a_{33} = -0.00020103830411805 \\
 a_{44} = -0.000175383550496096 \\
 a_{55} = -0.000050569034367109 \\
 a_{66} = -0.00000044208506829
 \end{cases}
 \quad (10)$$

Taking into account the found coefficients, we round them for the calculations convenience to the tenth decimal place and obtain a mathematical model of the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 35.150453840961281381 - \\
 & 0.01947314147950391 * x_1 + \\
 & 0.0015485321281696507 * x_2 -
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 0.00015111547700513 * x_3 + \\
 & 0.005633629965215796 * x_4 - \\
 & 0.001210291478275149 * x_5 - \\
 & 0.00000275368935526 * x_6 - \\
 & 0.00292586360758979 * x_1^2 - \\
 & 0.000000760152978526 * x_2^2 - \\
 & 0.00020103830411805 * x_3^2 - \\
 & 0.000175383550496096 * x_4^2 - \\
 & 0.000050569034367109 * x_5^2 - \\
 & 0.00000044208506829 * x_6^2 = y
 \end{aligned}$$

The next necessary step is to check the adequacy of the model, which allows you to determine how accurately it describes the modeled object. And here the first step is to find the pair and multiple correlations coefficients. Calculation for the average values of input and output parameters is carried out according to the formulas:

$$\bar{x}_i = \frac{\sum x_{ij}}{n} \quad \text{и} \quad \bar{y} = \frac{\sum y_j}{n} \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{x}_i$ and $\bar{y}$ are the average values of the input and output parameters, respectively, i is a parameter number, j is number of the i -th parameter measurement, n is measurements number.

The dispersion is calculated by the formulas:

$$D(x_i) = \frac{\sum x_{ij}^2}{n} - \bar{x}_i^2 \quad \text{и} \quad D(y) = \frac{\sum y_j^2}{n} - \bar{y}^2 \quad (12)$$

while the standard deviation is:

$$S(x_i) = \sqrt{D(x_i)} \quad \text{и} \quad S(y) = \sqrt{D(y)} \quad (13)$$

The value of the pair correlation coefficients is calculated separately for each of the input parameters using the formula:

$$r_{x_i y} = \frac{\overline{x_i y} - \bar{x}_i \bar{y}}{S(x_i) S(y)} \quad (14)$$

Formula (14) makes it possible to calculate the values of the pair correlation for the input parameters with respect to the output. In cases where pair correlation of 2 input parameters is being calculated, the output parameter y is replaced by one of the input parameters, different from the already used x_i . The result of the above calculations is Table 2 - a paired correlation coefficients matrix.

Table 2

		Pair correlation coefficients					
Y		X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5	X_6
Y	1	0,1350086	-0,0549872	0,6249195	0,0438308	0,348040	0,0803782
X_1	0,13500868	1	0,3471398	-0,1542979	-0,3041375	-0,1792898	0,3679425
X_2	-0,0549872	0,3471398	1	-0,0304792	0,2103348	-0,3221729	-0,9360010
X_3	0,6249195	-0,1542978	-0,0304792	1	-0,3097407	-0,703396	-0,1756585
X_4	0,0438308	-0,3041375	0,2103348	-0,3097407	1	-0,3665972	0,2345418
X_5	0,348040	-0,1792898	-0,3221729	-0,7033960	-0,3665972	1	-0,404376
X_6	0,0803782	0,3679425	-0,9360010	-0,1756585	0,2345418	-0,404376	1

After constructing the paired coefficients matrix, the next step is to calculate the multiple correlation coefficient. One of the ways to calculate it is the calculation by the formula:

$$R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\Delta_r}{\Delta_{r11}}} \quad (15)$$

where Δ_r is determinant of the paired correlation coefficients matrix, Δ_{r11} is determinant of the interfacorial correlation matrix.

Having calculated the necessary determinants, we obtain the following value of the multiple correlation coefficient:

$$R = 0,983546206 \quad (16)$$

The calculations results show that there is a high-level relationship between the parameters chosen for constructing the regression equation.

The next step is to evaluate the statistical reliability of the regression equation, which is carried out using the Fisher criterion, which requires the calculation of

the determination coefficient, which is the multiple correlation coefficient raised to the 2nd power:

$$F = \frac{R^2}{1-R^2} \frac{(n-m-1)}{m} \quad (17)$$

where R^2 is determination coefficient, n is observations number, m is parameters (factors) number.

The obtained value of the Fisher criterion is compared with the table value and, if it exceeds it, then the constructed model is statistically reliable. Considering that the observations number is $n=20$, and the factors number is $m=5$, we obtain the Fisher value: $F=7.14258009540836000$. Using the Fisher table for the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, for our system we obtain the tabular value $F_{Tab}=2.96$. Considering that the numerical value obtained by us is greater than the tabular one, it can be argued that the resulting regression model is quite adequate.

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PROCESS CONTROL OF CATALYTIC CRACKING

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Abstract

In the technological processes of the oil refining industry, the use of various functional apparatuses connected in various structures and the technological process continuity lead to the control complexity. Catalytic cracking plays a key role in the destructive oil refining process to meet the industry in gasoline needs. The main purpose of the catalytic cracking process is to obtain a gasoline high-octane component, but other valuable petroleum products are also obtained during this process. For this reason, one of the most important issues is the search for the optimal mode of technological process operation, the choice and justification of modern automation tools in accordance with the standards for the optimal implementation of the flow of this technological process.

Keywords: technological process, oil refining, catalytic cracking, high-octane component, vacuum distillate.

The catalytic cracking process has been deeply studied, many experimental observations have been made at various installations, and according to the studies carried out, it can be concluded that a large volume of both physical and chemical process flows is observed within this complex [1÷3].

One of the main blocks for the catalytic cracking unit (type "Q-43-107M") is the reactor block. This unit is used for catalytic cracking of vacuum distillate. Vacuum distillate supplied to this plant as a raw material is obtained from the primary oil refining unit, and one of the resulting oil products is vacuum distillate [4].

Currently, work is underway to modernize the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery plant, including the catalytic cracking unit. Since the modernization is complex,

these procedures also affect the automatic control system of this unit. Thus, the question arose about the integrated design of the automatic control system for the catalytic cracking unit. In the solving process this problem, a problems number emerged:

- low accuracy of used instrumentation and automation equipment;
- long delays in automatic tuning cycles;
- low quality of compressed air supplied to the pneumatic system.

Based on all this, we can say that it is impossible to solve the above problem using local instrumentation and automation tools that work with the existing old pneumatic automation, that is, it is impossible to create